

Carbothermal Treatment Of Metallurgical Residues For Use As A Supplementary Cementitious Material

Anna C. Krammer^{1,*}, Klaus Doschek-Held¹, Florian R. Steindl², Christoph Gatschlhofer¹, Joachim Juhart²

¹Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Franz-Josef-Straße 18, 8700 Leoben, Austria; ²Graz University of Technology, Rechbauerstraße 12, 8010 Graz, Austria; *(anna.krammer@unileoben.ac.at).

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1. Introduction

The cement industry is a major contributor to global CO₂ emissions, with approximately 93 Mt CO₂ from cement production in the EU-27 alone per year. The target is to reduce the CO₂ emissions to 472 kg/t cement by 2030, with 24 kg CO₂/t cement through clinker substitution. [1, 2] Supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) are used to replace clinker to reduce cement production's environmental impact partially. This is done to decrease the clinker-to-cement ratio, as clinker production is the most CO₂-intensive step in the process. However, the availability of the commonly used SCMs is decreasing, among other things, due to the efforts of the iron and steel industry to reduce its own carbon footprint by shifting the steel production towards the electric arc furnace (EAF) route, which is less carbon-intensive than the traditional blast furnace (BF) and basic oxygen furnace (BOF) route. [3] In 2018, GGBFS production in Europe reached 20.7 million tons, with 80.3% of this being used for cement and concrete production. However, only 5.4 % of the 16.3 million tons of steel mill slag produced were used in the cement and concrete industry and 4.5 million tons were deposited or temporarily stored. Additionally, the valuable metal content of these metallurgical residues is lost by using the majority for road construction despite the potential benefits for a circular economy. [4] More recent data show that the EU's crude steel production is around 152.6 million tons - 56 % from the BF/BOF route and 44% from the EAF route - resulting in approximately 43 million tons of slags, including around 22 million tons of GGBFS. [5] Therefore, the objective of this work is to explore the potential benefits of using carbothermally treated metallurgical residues as SCM for reducing CO₂ emissions in the cement industry. Additionally, the aim is to investigate the possibility of obtaining a secondary raw material as an iron-rich metal fraction through the carbothermal reduction of these residues. The overarching goal is to highlight the opportunity of promoting a circular economy in the iron and steel and cement industry by avoiding landfilling and maximizing resource utilization.

2. Materials and Methods

The focus of this study was on examining different metallurgical residues, which can be categorized into two main input materials: hot metal desulphurization slag (HMDS) and continuous casting slag (CCS), both of which are metallurgical residues from voestalpine Stahl Donawitz GmbH (VASD). These input materials were then subjected to further treatment steps, which required the use of correction materials to adjust the chemical composition of the output materials, particularly their CaO and SiO₂ contents. Calcium was sourced from basic oxygen furnace slag (BOFS) obtained from the same integrated steel mill, while SiO₂ was obtained from Siemens-Martin slag (SMS) from the VASD landfill site. All four materials were mixed in a defined composition, and carbon powder was added as a reducing agent for the carbothermal reduction. The mixture was then heated up to 1400°C in an inductively heated graphite crucible. After a holding time of around 30 minutes, the molten material was wet granulated. The rapid cooling of the thermochemically treated material is necessary for the use as SCM as a high amorphous content is required for the latent hydraulic properties. Subsequently, the granulate was dried and crushed, and the treated slag fraction was magnetically separated from the reduced metal fraction. The test was carried out four times with the same mixture to consider the

reproducibility (treated slags A – D). **Figure 1** summarizes the chemical modification of the metallurgical residues and defines the chemical boundaries for SCM suitability.

Figure 1. Left ternary diagram: chemical characterization of the metallurgical residues as input material. Right ternary diagram: chemical composition of the initial mixture and the four treated slags (A–D) in comparison to GGBFS. The red line defines the chemical boundaries for SCM suitability.

SCM Suitability. The activity index (AI) was measured according to ÖNORM EN 15167-1. [6] But instead of using the standardized 1:1 ratio for the test, prisms containing three parts CEM I 42.5 R and one part treated slag, was applied, agreeing with ÖNORM B 3309-1. [7] Additionally, the reactivity of the generated slag fraction was determined using the measurement of the hydration heat after 7 days according to the R³ testing method. [8]

3. Results and Discussion

The obtained slag fraction showed equivalent characteristics to the reference GGBFS within the scope of the applied testing methods. However, the AI after 28 days for the treated slag fraction was lower, but the hydration heat after 7 days was higher than that of the GGBFS. Further, the glass content and the flow temperature were measured and can also be seen in **Table 1**. In addition, the metal characterization indicates that the requirement for the iron content could be achieved for all samples. With regard to the reproducibility, low deviations between the four tests can be seen but for the manganese recovery.

Table 1. Results of the obtained slag fractions (A–D) regarding their SCM suitability and flow temperature in comparison to GGBFS and metal characterization

	requirement	A	B	C	D	GGBFS
SCM suitability						
glass content	> 66 %	99	99	98	99	98
activity index 28 days	> 90 %	96	96	96	96	103
hydration heat after 7 days	> 250 J/g _{slag}	540	532	517	547	407
material data						
flow temperature	- °C	1389	1387	1403	1375	1363
metal characterization						
Fe content	ca. 80 wt.-%	80	81	81	79	-
Mn content	- wt.-%	9	7	8	10	-
Cr content	- wt.-%	1	1	1	1	-

*activity index was measured on material obtained from replicate experiments

The carbothermal reduction of the mixture generated about 70 % of the treated slag fraction and 20% of the metal fraction. Assuming all metallurgical residues excluding the GGBFS in the EU-27 are treated with this method and the valuable metal content is not variable, this process would result in 14.7 million tons of SCM and 4.2 million tons of iron metal fraction as a secondary raw material for steel production. The remaining part consists of the gaseous phase and processing losses.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrated how metallurgical residues from iron and steel production can be utilized as future SCM in the cement or concrete industry. Furthermore, it was shown that carbothermal reduction of these residues can effectively recover valuable metals, particularly iron, to provide a secondary raw material for the iron and steel industry. However, further research and optimization of materials and processes are necessary to fully understand this approach's potential and limitations and identify and address key influencing parameters for metal recovery and binder suitability. Through continued investigation and a successful upscaling to industrial scale, using treated metallurgical residues in cement production and metal recovery can be important in promoting sustainable and circular industrial practices.

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